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Hybrid Energy Systems

Bernhard Braunecker

The security of gas and electricity supply in Switzerland is currently and perhaps also in the next years at the center of public discussions. Pragmatic solutions that can be quickly implemented are demanded, and any conflicts with binding climate agreements are being verbally downplayed, as the aim is to find only interim solutions. This is politically understandable in view of the increasing public nervousness, but any intermediate concept should always be expandable to new sustainable solutions in the future.

One example is the gas-fired power plant, which has so far been frowned upon as a representative of fossil technology, but has good political chances of realization in the short term due to its undeniable positive features as will be shown. Its main disadvantages, such as the uncertain gas supply situation, the significant increase in gas prices and the unavoidable CO₂ emissions are accepted as lesser evils for the moment.

If the decision for gas-fired power plants once has been done, why not incorporate it into long-term strategies to avoid losing investment efforts and acquired know-how? Couldn't we consider scenarios that neutralize the disadvantages mentioned? Physicists know that inside a closed system problems can always be overcome by combining it with other systems to create new degrees of freedom. These so-called hybrid systems should not only add up the advantages of each subsystem, but also compensate for each other's disadvantages in the right way. To this end, we present next some suggestions: First, we describe the combination of gas power generators and CO₂-extraction systems, and secondly, we mention small nuclear power plants as central energy source for interesting application cases.

Modern combustion approaches

One interesting type of gas-fired power plants currently in discussion in Switzerland are modern Combined Cycle Gas Turbine power plants CCGT (Fig. 1)¹. They are technically mature, have a high efficiency, are commercially available at short notice and can be well integrated into existing local infrastructures².

In the working range from 0.1 to 40 MW, they can be ramped up to full load within a few minutes and thus can compensate for the power fluctuations of renewable energy sources, a first interesting hybrid approach. Different CCGT variants up to about 350 MW exist as well, but are more intended for continuous operation.

Funktionsweise einer
Gas- und Dampfturbinenanlage (GuD)

EnBW

Fig. 1: Schematic of a CCGT (from ²)

Gas-fired power plants are attractively priced: The Swiss Federal Office for Energy BFE quotes an investment sum of 800 ± 100 MCHF for 1 GW of generated power output³; other estimates assume 600 - 800 MCHF / GW. In both cases, one arrives at about 240 MCHF for a 300 MW plant. Operating costs are reported to be 8 MCHF / a, but the main problem is the gas price. Since they varied in 2022 between 27.33 and 70.04 USD / MMBtu⁴, which corresponds to 83.8 and 214.8 CHF / MWh, then for a 300 MW plant, producing 2.68 TWh / a, the gas costs would be between 220 and 565 MCHF / a⁵.

The uncertainty of gas supplies is a disadvantage, as Switzerland is dependent on imports of gas, most of which came until now from Russia. However, as this affects all European countries and new supply scenarios based on Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) are being intensively promoted throughout Europe, the problem probably will become of minor importance already in the medium term. In addition, important gas pipelines between the northern EU states and Italy already run through Switzerland, so that the physical access to LNG flows is guaranteed, regardless from which direction the gas would come, provided the political conditions are right. On the other hand, the CO₂ emission of the CCGTs is not ignorable, even if the specific emission with $K_{\text{CCGT}} = 0.4 \text{ t}_{\text{CO}_2} / \text{MWh}$ is already significantly improved compared to a 'normal' coal-fired power plant with $1 \text{ t}_{\text{CO}_2} / \text{MWh}$ ⁶.

In Switzerland eight mobile gasturbines TM2500 from General Electric are currently installed in Birr (AG) as emergency generators for power shortages. They should deliver 250 MW, and their CO₂ emission in 14 days is $50'750 \text{ t}_{\text{CO}_2}$ ⁷.

3 <https://www.bfe.admin.ch/bfe/de/home/news-und-medien/medienmitteilungen/mm-test.msg-id-90735.html>

4 https://ycharts.com/indicators/europe_natural_gas_price

5 The gas price in December 2022 was about 189 Euro/MWh in Switzerland.

6 <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/38910/umfrage/hoeheder-co2-emissionen-nach-kraftwerk/>

7 Faktenblatt Reservekraftwerk Birr: <https://www.bfe.admin.ch/bfe/de/>

1 The 'combined cycle gas turbine' (CCGT) is a two-step machine; first the hot gases drive a gas turbine and second, the still hot exhaust gases produce steam for running a steam turbine. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Combined_cycle_power_plant

2 <https://www.enbw.com/energie-entdecken/energieerzeugung/konventionelle-erzeugung/>

This corresponds to $K_{\text{Birr}} = 0.6 \text{ t}_{\text{CO}_2} / \text{MWh}$. But the installation is clearly intended as reserve power plant to be run only in exceptional situations, and climate-neutral operation through the use of CO_2 -free fuels is required.

CO₂ extraction parks

This disadvantage of a CCGT could be reduced or even eliminated in the long term if the emitted CO_2 is removed out of the air and physically and/or chemically bound, as envisaged by the **Orca** aggregates (Fig. 2) of the company ClimeWorks⁸. One could install several of these aggregates in corresponding CO_2 extractions parks near to the CO_2 emitters, in analogy to the wind parks with their fleet of wind turbines for electricity generation. It would also be thinkable to minimize installation and service costs by combining wind and CO_2 extraction modules in a common park outside agglomerations as another attractive hybrid approach.

Fig. 2: Orca extraction modules of ClimeWorks (from⁸)

Here is an estimate: An Orca binds $4 \cdot 10^3 \text{ t}_{\text{CO}_2} / \text{a}$ ⁹ at a power input of 1 MW. Its characteristic CO_2 -extraction factor is therefore $K_{\text{Orca}} = 4 \cdot 10^3 \text{ t}_{\text{CO}_2} / \text{MWa} \sim 0.4 \text{ t}_{\text{CO}_2} / \text{MWh}$ ^{10 11}. It can be seen that K_{Orca} is equal to the mentioned emission factor of a CCGT with $K_{\text{CCGT}} = 0.4 \text{ t}_{\text{CO}_2} / \text{MWh}$. This means that the total CCGT power produced would be consumed by the Orcas to sequester the CO_2 emissions of the CCGT, thus still a meaningless zero-sum game.

If, however, one would succeed to halve the CO_2 emissions of the CCGTs and to double the CO_2 binding capacity of the Orcas, neither of which seems to be unrealistic, one would have an attractive variant with this hybrid approach. Then a CCGT of 300 MW would generate $300 \text{ MW} \cdot 1/2 \cdot 4 \cdot 10^3 \text{ t}_{\text{CO}_2} / \text{MWa} = 6 \cdot 10^5 \text{ t}_{\text{CO}_2} / \text{a}$, which can be bound by $N_{\text{Orca}} \cdot 2 \cdot 4 \cdot 10^3 \text{ t}_{\text{CO}_2} / \text{a}$, i.e. by $N_{\text{Orca}} = 75$ Orcas.

If, in addition, technical improvements allow reducing the power requirement from 1 MW to 0.5 MW per Orca, the CO_2 park would need only 37.5 MW operating power, which

is 12.5 % of the 300 MW generated by the CCGT. And if one further succeeds to lower the price from the current 10 MCHF to 1 MCHF per Orca by larger production numbers, then the resulting investment costs of 75 MCHF would be in a reasonable proportion to the already mentioned investment costs of 240 MCHF for a 300 MW CCGT. However as already mentioned the actual gas costs are the main problem.

Modern nuclear approaches

Modern nuclear technology also offers attractive solutions in which considerable progress has been made in terms of economic efficiency and operational safety. Especially interesting for future applications are Small Modular Reactors (SMR), where according to¹² more than 80 designs are under development and deployment in 18 states. Further detailed information about SMRs can be found in¹³. Here we mention General Atomics' Energy Multiplier Module EM² (Fig. 3), a modular, grid-connected energy source with a net block power of 265 MW¹⁴. EM² is a helium-cooled reactor with a core exit temperature of 850°C. The reactor uses a "convert-and-burn" core design in which the fuel used is converted internally into fissile isotopes. A refill of fuel is required only every 30 years. The reactor is housed in a sealed containment below the bottom and is equipped with advanced passive safety methods to control heat removal and reactivity. EM² also uses a closed-cycle direct gas turbine to increase efficiency¹⁵. This impressing module shows a further advantage of modern nuclear concepts when comparing its generated power density factor of 10 kW/m² with 5 W/m² of solar- and 2 W/m² of wind technology¹⁶.

Fig. 3: EM² System of General Atomics (from¹³)

[home/versorgung/stromversorgung/winterreserve.html](https://home.versorgung/stromversorgung/winterreserve.html)

⁸ <https://climeworks.com/roadmap/orca>

⁹ An Orca aggregate consists of eight collector containers with an annual capture capacity of 500 tons each.

¹⁰ <https://www.srf.ch/wissen/nachhaltigkeit/co2-wunder-island-der-groesste-co2-staubsauger-der-welt-kommt-aus-der-schweiz>

¹¹ <https://ethz.ch/de/news-und-veranstaltungen/eth-news/news/2022/04/neues-eth-einhorn-climeworks-holt-600-millionen-franken.html>

¹² <https://aris.iaea.org/sites/Publications.html> and IAEA-ARIS booklet Advances in Small Modular Reactor Technology 2022 Edition

¹³ <https://world-nuclear.org/information-library/nuclear-fuel-cycle/nuclear-power-reactors/small-nuclear-power-reactors.aspx>

¹⁴ <https://www.ga.com/general-atomics-and-framatome-collaborate-to-develop-a-fast-modular-reactor>

¹⁵ <https://www.ga.com/nuclear-fission/advanced-reactors>

¹⁶ Presentation of A. Manera, ETH Zürich: <http://www.pg2.ch/events/ws2223/event.20221013/index.html>

eVinci™ Micro Reactor (Westinghouse) *

The eVinci™ micro reactor's design is based on space reactor technologies and best suited for energy consumers in remote locations. Due to its small size the reactor is transported by special flat-bed trucks. Modern heat pipe technology is used to extract the core heat. According to the manufacturer the key attributes are:

- Transportable energy generator
- Fully factory built, fueled and assembled
- Delivers combined heat and power – 5 MWe and up to 13MWt
- 8+ years of full power operation prior to refueling
- Target less than 30 days onsite installation
- High speed load following capability
- High reliability and minimal moving parts
- Capable of autonomous operation
- Near zero Emergency Planning Zone with small site footprint
- No spent fuel or waste storage on site
- Simplified decommissioning and remediation

* <https://www.westinghousenuclear.com/energy-systems/evinci-micro-reactor>

FMR in local hybrid plants

At the same time Fast Modular Reactors (FMR), i.e. micro-reactors of only about 10 - 50 MW, are in development. The FMR of General Atomics of 50 MW (see page 193 in ¹²) is expected to demonstrate reactor operation before 2030. These modern aggregates with their closed gas cooling circuits are further developments of the modules used in submarines, and they are foreseen for space applications, especially also for space nuclear propulsion. Here we mention the micro reactor eVinci from Westinghouse (see Box) with a technology and manufacturing readiness level of 5, where one expects nuclear demonstration in 2024 (see page 349 in ¹²).

As turnkey, small-volume and user-friendly reactors, they are ideally suited as autonomous energy modules in remote

Fig 4: Westinghouse's vision of the mobile micro reactor eVinci.

agglomerations in third world countries. They would not only ensure the supply of electricity for daily use at a modern level, but could also be used for the desalination of seawater and for the production of hydrogen as a propellant or for the cooling of large food halls. Another argument in their favor is that many regions in third world countries suffer from increasingly frequent catastrophes such as tornadoes and major floods, which usually paralyze the supply chains to many villages for a long time due to destroyed power lines. Autonomous FMRs, which are installed underground, are largely immune to this type of disruption.

Finally, it would be worth considering installing the above-mentioned CO₂ extraction parks as stand-alone plants in regions remote from civilization. Then an autonomous FMR of 40 MW would be a small volume, easy to install and maintenance-friendly energy source for such a novel park concept ¹⁷.

More global thinking in Switzerland

Switzerland, with its approximately eight million inhabitants, represents about 1 per mille of the world's population. It therefore contributes de-facto more or less about this small factor to the world's climate and environmental crises, but the same also holds for all the national efforts to mitigate the crises, such as reducing CO₂ emissions. It may therefore be asked, if the big financial means to substitute the combustion engine of all Swiss cars by an electric unit should not be better invested in new hybrid technologies that would allow billions of people in Africa, Asia and South America to improve their life quality? If new energy concepts could cause them to stop the burning of wood and coal, then the effect on the global environment would be much stronger than any national Swiss action. Switzerland has the necessary expertise in research and in industry and is part of many international networks. This strong competence would allow to transfer new hybrid technologies into mass products that would be affordable for third world countries.

Outlook

The global climate crisis and the shortage of energy supply cannot be solved by appeals for savings alone; what is needed are technical solutions whose advantages are accepted without hesitation. Hybrid approaches that combine the features of different technologies, so that the new system is more efficient, more flexible, more cost-effective and more easy to use than the individual subsystems, require high engineering competence. Switzerland could offer this to the world in order to solve the global problems there where the majority of them arises. If the living conditions of the population in third world countries can be improved at the same time, other crises triggered by the emigration flows of disillusioned people would hopefully also be significantly defused.

17 Idea of Rodrigo Braunecker-Sicilia (14 years old)